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EXPLORING STUDENTS' CONCEPTIONS OF VECTORS: A PHENOMENOGRAPHIC STUDY

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*“He cannot, England know, who knows England only.”
Ferenc Marton*

ABSTRACT

The concept of vector plays a central role in engineering mechanics and strength of materials, where many quantities are vectorial in nature. Phenomenographic studies can be useful in revealing the different perspectives of the students' understanding of vectors and variation theory is a promising approach to improve the teaching of vectors. In this study, we will use the frameworks of phenomenography and variation theory to explore students' understanding and difficulties in using the concept of vector. The data consists of pre-, post- and delayed post-tests questions about vectors as well as student project reports in the course “Models, Mechanics & Materials”, given to first-year engineering students, studying “Sustainable Design” at Aalborg University, Copenhagen, Denmark. The results of the pre-test suggest that most emphasis in teaching vectors in upper secondary school mathematics has been on the algebraic representations of vectors and less on their graphical representations, the mastery of which is essential to succeed in engineering courses such as mechanics and strength of materials. The results of the post- and delayed post-tests as well as the students' project reports showed some improvement in the

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students' performances after using variation- and context-based teaching of vectors in the course. The article concludes with some proposals on how the results of this study can be used to enhance the teaching and learning of vectors at the upper secondary schools and the university.

1 INTRODUCTION

Understanding many concepts in physics and engineering, such as force, moment and velocity, stands or falls on a firm grasp of the concept of vector [1]. Several studies investigate students' conceptions of vectors. For example, [2] investigated 2,031 physics students' understanding of vector addition, magnitude and direction. They prepared a list of questions about vectors in all introductory general physics courses at Iowa State University as pre- and post-tests. The outcomes showed that most of the students were unable to carry out two-dimensional vector addition after completing a physics course. [3] found that many students were not able to add or subtract vectors graphically after traditional instruction and could not answer qualitative questions about vector addition and subtraction. Their results are consistent with those of [2]: Students have difficulties performing basic vector operations. However, none of the previously mentioned studies investigating students' understanding of vectors utilized a phenomenographic perspective to design a lesson in vectors and to explore specific aspects in students' conceptions of vectors. This paper is an attempt to do so. Our empirical data consists of students' achievements on vectors through a pre-, post- and a delayed post-test as well as students' project reports in the course "Models, Mechanics & Materials", given to first-year engineering students in the years 2018-2019, studying "Sustainable Design" at Aalborg University, Copenhagen, Denmark.

Thus, the main purpose of the article is an investigation, using a phenomenographic perspective, whether the use of variation in teaching can contribute to improved learning of vectors. Variation theory is described below.

2 ON PHENOMENOGRAPHY AND VARIATION THEORY

How is it that two students who are sitting in the same class on the same day with access to the same materials can come to understand a vector (or any engineering concept for that matter) differently? There may be many answers to this question. "Variation theory is a theory of learning and experience that explains how a learner might come to see, understand, or experience a given phenomenon in a certain way" [4, p. 3391]. Variation theory stems from the phenomenographic tradition [5], which is an educational research method developed in the early 1980's by a research group at the Department of Education at the University of Gothenburg in Sweden [6]. It grew out of a series of empirical research studies that attempted to answer the questions "(1) What does it mean that some people are better learners than others? And (2) Why are some people better at learning than others?" [7, p. 146]. [6] asserts that there are a limited number of qualitatively unique ways in which different people experience or perceive the same phenomenon. Thus, the goal of phenomenographic research is to identify and describe the variation in experiences

or perceptions that students have of a given phenomenon. The phenomenon under study can *also* be a concept or an event.

Variation theory, sometimes referred to as “new phenomenography”, reflects a shift within the phenomenographic research tradition that occurred in the 1990s [4].

During that time, phenomenography was criticized as being a purely descriptive and theoretical framework. In other words, although phenomenography and its methods could be used to identify and describe the range of experiences a group of people had with a given phenomenon, it could not explain *why* that variation in experience existed. Variation theory can be seen as a more theoretical extension of phenomenography, in that it attempts to explain how students (and generally, people) can experience the same phenomenon differently and how that knowledge can be used to improve classroom teaching and learning [8]. One of the most important tenets of variation theory is that seeing differences precedes seeing sameness [9]. The quote mentioned at the top of this document illustrates this claim: You cannot possibly understand what English is simply by listening to different people speaking English if you have never heard another language. Similarly, you cannot possibly understand what a vector is by only inspecting different examples of vectors.

To gain a complete understanding of a phenomenon, four different patterns of variation have been identified. These signify the difference between the aspects that stay invariant in a learning situation and those that do not. These are [10]:

1. **Contrast:** A person needs a point of reference to compare something with something else.
2. **Generalisation:** Variation in values of that aspect is necessary to discern the phenomenon.
3. **Separation:** In order to be able to separate certain aspects from other aspects, the phenomenon must vary while other aspects remain invariant.
4. **Fusion:** In cases where the phenomenon must be experienced in its entirety, it is necessary that a situation should be present where these aspects are all experienced simultaneously. Therefore, there is a fusion within the dimensions of variation of the specific critical aspects.

In variation theory, a teaching situation involves the intersection of two domains of knowledge and experience, *the teacher sphere* and the *student sphere*. The knowledge processed during a teaching situation can have three different outcomes [11]:

- The intended object of learning is what the teacher initially intended the students to learn.
- The enacted object of learning is what is made possible by the teacher for the students to learn in the lesson.
- The lived object of learning is what the students actually learn as a result of a learning situation. This knowledge can be analysed both individually and groupwise.

The following representation of the three forms of knowledge is the authors' own modification of the model proposed by [12, p. 210].

Fig. 1. The three different perspectives of knowledge in variation theory

3 STUDY METHODOLOGY

The participants in the study are 42 first-year engineering students, enrolled in the study program “Sustainable Design” at Aalborg University, Copenhagen, Denmark. We chose these students because of convenience in sampling and also because the topics of the course can be found in many engineering programs. The students were given a pre-test in the first day of class of the course “Models, Mechanics & Materials”, held in the Fall semester 2018. The first author was the lecturer in the course. The pre-test includes many questions about basic topics from upper secondary school mathematics, including the following two questions about vectors:

1. By referring to Fig. 2 below, it is given that $|\vec{a}| = 4$ and $|\vec{b}| = 3$. Sketch the vector $\vec{a} + \vec{b}$ and calculate its length (numerical value).
2. By referring to Fig. 3 below, it is given that $|\vec{a}| = |\vec{b}| = 5$. Sketch the vector $\vec{a} - \vec{b}$ and calculate its length (numerical value).

Fig. 2. Two perpendicular vectors

Fig. 3. Two oblique vectors

These questions are chosen because they represent some *critical features* of a vector (in contrast to a scalar, for example). The post-test and the delayed post-test consist of the same questions as the pre-test. The post-test was conducted at the end of the course in December 2018, where the students also had to submit a group report in the course project. The same class received the delayed post-test at the end of the Spring semester in June 2019.

The results of the tests are collected and analysed, while the students' project reports are made accessible on Aalborg University learning platform, *Moodle*. Assessing the students' prior knowledge through a pre-test would make the students aware of the contents they are expected to learn and can potentially influence the learning experience of the students [13].

The purpose of the delayed post-test is to analyse the lived knowledge of the students as well as to enable the researcher to see whether the changes in knowledge have a long-term effect or only a short-term effect of the lesson. As educators and researchers, we are naturally interested in developing sustainable learning, since tests given directly after the lesson are not indicators of long-term change in the students' experience.

4 LESSON DESIGN

According to variation theory, the role of the teacher is to design learning experiences for students to make it possible for them to discern the critical features of the object of learning [14, p. 195]. However, variation in teaching does not guarantee that the student will in fact discern the object of learning at stake, as discerning depends on the student's previous knowledge, current state of mind, interest in learning, etc. The curriculum of the course Mathematics A at the upper secondary education in Denmark (highest level) involves an introduction to two-dimensional vectors [15], mainly in coordinate form. Examining some textbooks that implement the curriculum, for example [16], the authors found that the concept of vector is used merely as a synonymous of free vector, which is not enough for the university students to discern all the critical features of a vector, as applied in the course. Variation is therefore needed to discern those aspects of vectors not previously discerned by learners. Using variation and simultaneity between aspects, the students can learn to see vectors in new ways.

Presumably, the students have studied vectors as quantities having both a magnitude and direction in contrast to scalars, which only have a magnitude. Below we give excerpts of the actual lesson on vectors given by the first author. We started by reminding the students of what they have learned about vectors and scalars by giving examples, as in the following figure:

<u>Scalars & Vectors</u>		
<u>Scalar</u>	vs	<u>Vector</u>
Distance		Displacement
Speed		Velocity
Mass		Force
Temperature		Acceleration

Fig. 4. Scalars and vectors

We then asked the students to *compare* and *contrast* the vectors in the following two figures. In Fig. 5, the velocity of the rocket test sled is a *free vector* since the velocity is the same at all points in the sled whereas the two force vectors in Fig. 6 are *fixed* (or *bound*) since changing their positions will alter their effects on the mattress. The velocity vector in Fig. 5 corresponds to the *mathematical* definition of a vector (read: *free vector*). In Fig. 6, the two aspects magnitude and direction remained *invariant* while the point of application varied. This situation corresponds to the *separation of aspects* in variation theory.

Fig. 5. A free vector

Fig. 6. Fixed vectors

We then showed the students two different examples of a *sliding vector*. In Fig. 7, the four cable forces can “slide” along their respective lines of action, *along* the cables, similar to the weights of the two traffic lights in Fig. 8 which can also “slide” along their respective lines of action, but *perpendicular* to the horizontal beam.

Fig. 7. Sliding vectors (I)

Fig. 8. Sliding vectors (II)

A fusion of all aspects of a vector results when we generalize the mathematical definition of a vector, by giving our own definition:

- A vector is a quantity that has a magnitude, direction, line of action *and* a point of action.
- If the line of action does not pass through a certain point in space, the vector is called a *free vector*. It is freely movable in space
- If the line of action is fixed, the vector is called a *sliding vector*. It does not have a unique point of action.
- If the point of action is unique, the vector is called a *fixed vector*.

5 RESULTS OF THE STUDY

The focus of this section is on whether teaching vectors using variation theory has contributed to improve the students' understanding of some critical features of vectors. 42 students took the three tests, but only 40 answered to the delayed post-test.

Table 1. Distribution of conceptions between Pre-, Post- og delayed post-test

Student conception	Pre-test scores	Post-test scores	Delayed post-test scores
1) Sketching $\vec{a} + \vec{b}$	70%	91%	74%
2) Finding $ \vec{a} + \vec{b} $	72%	80%	79%
3) Sketching $\vec{a} - \vec{b}$	27%	61%	53%
4) Finding $ \vec{a} - \vec{b} $	20%	39%	32%

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation (SD) for students' achievement in the three tests

Test	Mean	SD
Pre	1.86	1.08
Post	2.80	0.97
Delayed post	2.2	1.05

In order to find out if the differences between the scores of the pre-test and the delayed post-test were significantly different, or not, a paired *t*-test was conducted:

T Test, Difference of Means

	Sample 1	Sample 2
Mean	1.86	2.2
s	1.08	1.05
N	42	40
SE	0.2352	
df	79.964	
t	-1.4454	
P	0.0761	

Fig. 9. Results of a statistical test to compare the two means of the pre-test and the delayed post-test

As seen in Tables 1 and 2, the students achieved significantly better test scores in the post- and delayed post-tests than in the pre-test although the delayed post-test scores were all a little below the post-test scores. For example, there was a considerable increase in the students' scores on sketching the difference vector $\vec{a} - \vec{b}$ from 27% in the pre-test to 53% in the delayed post-test. A close look at the results of the pre-test showed that many students who gave wrong answers in finding the length $|\vec{a} - \vec{b}|$, have erroneously used Pythagoras' theorem to calculate the length, which they have previously learned in connection with finding the length of a vector, given in coordinate form. This would suggest that the geometrical aspects of vectors were given a minor role, whereas the *algebra* of vectors is much more dominant at the upper secondary school. In fact, the length and direction of a vector are critical geometrical features of a vector that cannot be discerned *merely* by using vector coordinates.

The paired *t*-test (Fig. 9) found the *p*-value to be 0.0761, which means that we can reject the null-hypothesis that the mean difference between the two sets of answers is zero at a 10% significance level, but not at a 5% significance level. Thus the students did in fact score somewhat higher in the post-delayed test on average.

It seems, therefore, that using variation theory as a lesson design tool *together* with teaching vectors in the *context* of statics and strength of materials would improve students' learning in vectors. This study imparts some empirical evidence that support the use of variation theory as a pedagogical guide to design lessons in vectors in the classroom.

In the figures below, we show excerpts of some students' answers.

Fig. 10. A student solution for finding $\vec{a} + \vec{b}$ in the pre-test. The length is however correct

Fig. 11. A student solution for finding $|\vec{a} - \vec{b}|$ in the pre-test. Notice the use of coordinates and Pythagoras' Theorem

Fig. 12. A student solution for finding $\vec{a} - \vec{b}$ in the pre-test

Fig. 13. A student solution for finding $\vec{a} - \vec{b}$ in the delayed post-test

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS AND DISCUSSION

Variation theory is a promising tool for investigating students' conceptual understanding. However, the authors find that the theory ignores the effects of the students' prior knowledge on the lived object of learning. In fact, some studies have shown that the students' prior knowledge affects their learning when comparing multiple examples in teaching [17]. The students' prior knowledge itself could be thought of as a pre-lived object of learning, while students' understanding of the object of learning after the learning event takes place could be a post-lived object of learning. However, each individual encounters a unique set of experiences that shapes a unique cognitive framework and guides the perception and integration of new knowledge within the individual. Thus, prior knowledge is an important element in the construction of conceptual knowledge [18]. That is why we decided to integrate the students' prior knowledge about vectors to construct a new understanding of vectors, which itself becomes part of the students' prior knowledge for a future learning experience. As seen in Tables 1 and 2 and Figure 9, the results of the delayed post-test seem to suggest that the students did not fully retain what was learnt, but the fact that a lot was retained means that this knowledge would indeed

become part of the pre-lived object of learning. Furthermore, when the students took the delayed post-test, they were busy with the actual exams and motivating them to take this test for the benefit of research was not easy, which might also explain the drop.

In this regard, the authors suggest that the curriculum of vectors in Mathematics A at the upper secondary schools and in engineering mathematics courses should include all kinds of vectors that the students will encounter in science and engineering, given the fact that many students enrolled in Mathematics A will study science, mathematics, engineering or technology at the university.

Since instructional materials, including both physical and virtual resources, are designed to facilitate learning [19], they can have an unintended influence on the enacted object of knowledge. Therefore, the authors call for the inclusion of more examples on the geometrical aspects of vectors and their applications in physics and engineering in upper secondary mathematics textbooks.

7 FUTURE RESEARCH PERSPECTIVES

Recent research studies reported that the integration of variation theory in classroom instruction improves students' performance significantly [20, 21]. Considering the success of the integration of variation theory in teaching vectors, it is possible to combine variation theory, *animations* and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) in major topics of the course, such as equilibrium of rigid bodies, materials behaviour and stress analysis, by allowing students to construct their own knowledge. Studying the different forms of the objects of learning during their three phases: the intended, the enacted (read: *constructed*) and the lived, and the influence they would have on the learning outcomes of the whole course, would be an interesting subject for a future article.

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